

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates: 7 – 15 November 2022

Report published: October 2023

**Elephant encounters:
Studying Asian elephants in the hills of
northern Thailand to increase their
welfare and conservation**

มูลนิธิหัวใจรักช้าง
Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary
Love. Care. Rescue.

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**Authors:
Aislinn Butron, Alex Johncola, Talia Gale
Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary**

**Matthias Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions**

Abstract

This report is the result of a fourth year of collaboration between Biosphere Expeditions and Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary (KSES). The 2022 expedition took place from 7 to 15 November. Seven citizen scientists collected data on elephant foraging, association and behaviour in the northern region of Thailand, in a community forest of 4000 acres.

Direct observation methods were used by citizen scientists to collect three separate datasets (activity budgeting via instantaneous sampling, foraging habits via all-occurrence focal sampling and social-association behaviour via scan sampling) on six free-roaming semi-wild Asian elephants.

Ninety-six hours of activity budget data collected on each of the six elephants showed that they spent the majority of their time foraging, followed by exploring, which is comparable to wild Asian elephants. There was no significant difference between the behaviours displayed by the six elephants.

The foraging data collected during the expedition showed a high variety of plant species foraged on (23 species from three different families). The elephants foraged almost exclusively on browse (96%) rather than graze species (1%), however there was (3%) foraging on unidentified foliage. There was no significant difference in the plant species that they foraged on.

The elephant association data set used the proximity of the study subjects to examine social affiliation and closeness among the elephants. The elephants had varying social preferences. Four elephants regularly associated with one another, but did not consistently segregate into distinct groups. One male elephant was mostly observed on his own, for a total of only five associations data points collected. Close association was commonly observed amongst the three females and less in the teenage males. The difference in male and female associations can be used to help reintroduce male elephants in our herd.

Based on this, KSES here makes various recommendations on improving animal welfare in terms of captive elephant food and space provision and ethical ways of re-introducing captive elephants into semi-wild conditions, given the lack of forest to reintroduce them into and the significant potential for human-wildlife conflict if captive elephants were simply to be “re-wilded” into available forest areas. KSES can and wants to act as a showcase of how re-introduction can and should be done, benefiting all concerned: the animals, their mahout handlers and the community they are to be semi-rewilded into. KSES also aims to publish a paper on elephant association by 2025, supplementing the paper on diet already published in 2020 and working towards an elephant welfare guide to be distributed to elephant venues in Thailand and around the world by 2026.

างยั้ง เพื่อให้เกิดประโยชน์ต่อทุกฝ่ายที่เกี่ยวข้อง ไม่ว่าจะเป็นช้าง ความรู้ช้างผู้ดูแล
และชุมชนที่ช้างจะถูกนำไปเลี้ยงในสภาพกึ่งป่า KSES
ยังได้ตั้งเป้าหมายที่จะตีพิมพ์บทความเกี่ยวกับพฤติกรรมของช้างภายในปี 2025
ต่อเนื่องจากบทความเกี่ยวกับอาหารช้างที่ได้รับการตีพิมพ์ไปแล้วในปี 2020
และอยู่ระหว่างการดำเนินการจัดทำคู่มือแนวทางการจัดการช้าง เพื่อแจกจ่ายไปยังปางช้างต่างๆ
ในประเทศไทยและทั่วโลกภายในปี 2026

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1. Expedition Review

Matthias Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions

1.1. Background

Background information, location conditions and the research area are as per Johncola et al. (2019). This expedition conducted close-encounter studies on a herd of six Asian elephants at Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary (KSES) in the hills of Northern Thailand. All studies were solely observational with no interaction between the elephants and researchers. A thorough outline of the current situation regarding elephants in Thailand is given in the introduction of chapter 2.

1.2. Dates & team

The expedition ran over an 8-day period from 7 to 15 November 2022. The expedition team was composed of national and international citizen scientists, a professional scientist and an expedition leader. The study period was chosen to coincide with the mildest climate in terms of temperature extremes and high forest food availability for the elephants.

The expedition scientist and co-author of this report was Aislinn Butron, the expedition leader was Anthony Lyons. The expedition team of citizen scientists was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence): Michaela Agari (Germany), Julia Brechenmacher (Germany), Andreas Dank (Germany), Ursula Kleinbach (Germany), George Rheinhardt (Germany), Charles Ritterband* (Austria) and Valeria Zhavoronkina (USA). / *journalist: See coverage (in German) in MaDeRe magazine about the [study elephants](#) and the [expedition host village](#).

A medical umbrella, safety and evacuation procedures were in place, but did not have to be invoked, because there were no significant medical or other incidences (there was a sprained ankle, which was treated on site).

1.3. Partners

On this expedition Biosphere Expeditions' main partner was Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary (KSES), a fellow nonprofit organisation. Their main objective is to bring elephants back to their natural environment to live in semi-wild conditions and provide an alternative and sustainable livelihood.

1.4. Acknowledgements

The expedition provided labour and funding, and permitted data collection to occur throughout the day, allowing for full data sets on KSES's elephants to be collected. We are grateful to the citizen scientists, who not only dedicated their spare time to helping but also, through their expedition contributions, funded the research. A big thank you to all the members of the local community, especially those who welcomed expedition participants into their homes with open arms, who guided us through the forest, who helped with transportation and who cooked amazing meals. Biosphere Expeditions would also like to thank members of the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions and donors for their support.

1.5. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts and a copy of this report can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org.

Project updates, reports and publications:

<https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

All expedition reports, including this and previous expedition reports:

<https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Expedition diary/blog:

<https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/thailand-2022/>

Expedition details, background, pictures, videos, etc.

<https://www.biosphere-expeditions.org/thailand>

1.6. Expedition budget

Each citizen scientist paid a contribution of €1,960 per person per nine-day group towards expedition costs. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, special research equipment and all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs etc., or visa and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how this contribution was spent are given below.

Income	€
Expedition contributions	15,895
Expenditure	
Staff	4,795
includes local and Biosphere Expeditions staff salaries and travel expenses	
Research	129
includes equipment and other research expenses	
Transport	492
includes fuel, taxis and other local transport	
Expedition base	1,775
includes board & lodging and base hut upgrade	
Administration	133
includes miscellaneous fees & sundries	
Team recruitment Thailand	3,998
as estimated % of annual PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	
Income – Expenditure	4,573
Total percentage spent directly on project	71%

2. Activity budgeting, foraging and social behaviour of free-roaming semi-wild Asian elephants

Aislinn Butron, Alexandra Johncola & Talia Gale
Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary

2.1 Introduction

Population dynamics of wild & captive elephants in Thailand

Asian elephants (*Elephas maximus*) are acknowledged as a megaherbivore, the largest terrestrial animal, as well as keystone species, with a wide span of habitat presence, ranging from tropical to sub-tropical regions (Suksavate et al. 2019). In Thailand, the estimated total number of elephants ranges from 6783-7483, with 3783 held in captivity and 3000-3500 in the wild (Thitaram et al. 2015, Asian Elephant Specialist Group 2017). As the global population size declines in countries across Asia, the population of elephants in Thailand is also experiencing a downward trend due to habitat loss, habitat fragmentation and anthropogenic pressure. The global population of Asian elephants currently sits between 40,000-52,000 individuals and is categorised as Endangered by the IUCN (IUCN 2020).

History and cultural significance of Asian elephants in Thailand

Elephants have been a fundamental part of Thai culture since the 13th century (Bansiddhi et al. 2020), with animals playing a role in warfare, religion, culture, logging, and now tourism. Industrialisation brought with it a steep decline in forest cover, resulting in a decline in wild elephant populations. In 1989 the logging industry was banned with 25% of forest cover remaining. Subsequent demand for agricultural land, loss of habitat and habitat fragmentation left 70% percent of working elephants out of a home and out of work. Many elephants together with their caretakers (mahouts) were left to earn a living in cities, which created dangerous environments for the public in major cities. As a result, the Thai government began to classify elephant populations into wild and captive elephants. Wild populations were under the protection of the Wild Animal Reservation and Protection Act 1992, which prohibited capturing, killing, and injuring elephants (Nijman 2014).

Rewilding and wild elephant populations in Thailand

The dramatic decrease in wild elephant populations led to efforts to increase and stabilise their numbers. In 1997 HRH Queen Sirikit of Thailand created the first project to introduce formerly captive elephants to national parks. Since then 104 elephants have been released (Mithapala 2009, Thitaram et al. 2015, Baker & Winkler 2020). However, there are limitations to rewilding projects through habitat loss, habitat fragmentation and human-elephant conflict. There is also often increased conflict with humans, for example through crop raiding, where there is reintroduction of captive elephants.

Captive elephant populations in Thailand

Captive elephants are considered livestock in Thailand and are not awarded animal welfare protection by the Draught Animal Act of 1939 (Nijman 2014). As such, the Thai government needed to create employment for captive elephants. Today, and for the past five decades, this employment is predominantly in tourism (Bansiddhi et al. 2020), an increasingly important factor in Thailand's economy. Indeed, by 2018 Thailand's travel and tourism had become a critical component of the national gross domestic product, at 21.6% (World Travel & Tourism Council 2020). This growth in tourism in general also results in increased demand for animal-based tourism, especially elephant tourism. The National Institute of Elephant Research, Health Service, and Department of Livestock Development estimate that there are a minimum of 2700 elephants working in 250 tourist venues throughout Thailand (Bansiddhi et al. 2020). Activities with elephants range from observation, feeding, bathing, walking, riding to elephant entertainment and shows. However, there are increasing concerns about elephant welfare as well as exploitative and abusive treatment¹.

Current welfare implications

In Thailand, ethical welfare standards and animal-based tourism do not co-exist naturally (Bansiddhi et al 2018). This, alongside the challenges of too many elephants for too few wild spaces and the difficulties of reintroduction where it does happen, results in lively debates about what to do with Thailand's elephants (ASEAN 2015, Schmidt-Burbach 2017, Bansiddhi et al. 2018, Baker & Winkler 2020). For example, Bansiddhi et al. (2018) argue that tourist camps are the only viable solution for providing care for captive elephants, as the demand for elephants in the tourist industry is unlikely to wane in the near future. Baker & Winkler (2020) argue that campaigns to educate tourists might encourage tourist companies to shift activities with elephants to more welfare-oriented hands-off programmes.

Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary project

Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary (KSES) is an NGO that is focused on creating an alternative option for tourism regarding captive elephants in Thailand. Its main mission is to bring back elephants to the forest by offering hands-off elephant tourism, which provides an income for the NGO, the elephant mahouts and the local community, and also allows for the elephants to lead near natural lives. The hands-off tourist programme allows guests to hike with and see elephants in their natural habitat. The project also focuses on improving the welfare standards of elephants by conducting research. Currently there are three research areas focused on elephant foraging, behaviour and association. By collecting and analysing data, with Biosphere Expeditions' help, KSES hopes to publish findings to a wide scientific audience, thereby helping to elucidate the complex situation, while also showcasing that alternative approaches that benefit elephants and people can work. In 2020, KSES published its first research paper (Schwarz et al. 2020) that identified over 160 species of plants consumed by elephants. In 2025 KSES hopes to publish a second research paper on elephant behaviour, followed by an elephant welfare guide in 2026.

¹ <https://www.usnews.com/news/best-countries/articles/2022-11-14/advocates-raise-alarms-about-tourisms-toll-on-thai-elephants>

COVID-19

During the outbreak of COVID-19, KSES was forced to close its doors for 2.5 years. No data collection took place during this time. KSES was not the only project affected by COVID-19; all tourism in Thailand had closed down, including elephant tourist attractions. Many elephants, alongside their mahouts, were forced to return to their villages without any financial help, further compromising animal welfare, with owners frequently unable to provide for their elephants. During the pandemic KSES saw an influx of 70+ elephants into the community forest and began fundraising for elephant fodder. Re-opening in September 2022 allowed KSES slowly to rebuild the project and data collection.

2.2 Materials and methods

The study site, animals as well as materials & methods are as per Johncola et al (2019).

In summary, KSES is home to six elephants. All of these elephants were previously working elephants in the logging industry or in tourist camps. Too Meh is female and the oldest elephant in the herd (60 years old). Mae Doom (female, late 20s) is the daughter of Too Meh and is the aunt of Dodo and Gen Thong. Gen Thong (male, 10 yo) is the youngest elephant in the herd. Dodo (17 yo) is Gen Thong's older brother. Boon Rott (male, 17 yo) is unrelated to the other elephants in the herd. Lastly, Sri Prai (female, 11 yo) is also unrelated to the rest of the herd.

The partnership with Biosphere Expeditions enables KSES to collect scientific data on various elephants simultaneously, while also collecting data at varying times of the day.

The two-day training period, which included a training hike and data collection period was designed to familiarise citizen scientists with the conditions and expectations of collecting field data (e.g. walking on steep hillsides while recording elephant behaviour). All citizen scientists were required to pass an elephant identification and behaviour test prior to collecting data to ensure accurate data collection and quality. Citizen scientists were then divided each day into changing groups to reflect the research projects (four citizen scientists on behaviour activity budgets, two sets of four on association, two on foraging).

Statistical analysis of activity budget: At each interval, if a single behaviour was observed, it was given a value of 1; if two behaviours were observed simultaneously, they were each given a value of 0.5. Incidences recorded as 'cannot see' were omitted from the analysis. Social bathing and social foraging were added to the 'socialising' category and drinking, rolling and digging were added to the 'other' category. A one-way ANOVA ($\alpha = 0.05$, $n = 5$) was performed across the behaviours for the elephants.

Foraging statistical analysis was done via a one-way ANOVA ($\alpha = 0.05$, $n = 5$) in Microsoft Excel, comparing foraging encounters of each elephant.

2.3. Results

Activity budget

An average of 144 incidents of behaviours were recorded for each elephant, for a collective total of 864 incidences. For 215 (25%) incidences, the elephants were out of sight (recorded as 'cannot see'). Out of 16 behaviours listed on the ethogram (Johncola et al, 2019), the elephants displayed 14 behaviours. Sex was the only behaviour not observed. Foraging was the most prominent behaviour observed (47%), followed by walking (16%), exploring (8%), socializing and standing (both at 7%), bathing and scratching (both at 3%), social foraging, dusting and drinking (all at 2%), mahout interaction and other (1% or less). (Figure 2.2a). The mean temperature for each hour interval of data collection ranged from 26°C to 27°C. There was no significant difference in the behaviours observed for the six individual elephants ($F=0.268$, $p=0.928$).

Figure 2.2a. Pooled percentage of time the elephants spent performing behaviours

Elephant foraging

661 minutes of foraging data were recorded, with 23 different species consumed, 18 of which were identified to the genus level, three to family and two to local names. The plants consumed and identified come from thirteen different families: Fabaceae (5 species), Poaceae (3 species), Primulaceae (2 species), Anacardiaceae (2 species) and, as well as one species each for Tiliaceae, Dioscoreaceae, Lythraceae, Araliaceae, Arecaea, Dipterocarpaceae, Solanaceae, Vitaceae and Malvaceae (Table 2.2.a).

Table 2.2a. Plant species consumed by the elephants during the 2022 expedition.

Plant	Type	Part(s) consumed	% of foraging encounters
<i>Acacia</i> sp (Gleh) Fabaceae	Tree	Leaves	3.93%
Bamboo (Vami) Poaceae	Bamboo	Leaves	47.20%
Bamboo (Vasu) Poaceae	Bamboo	Leaves	3.18%
<i>Bauhinia</i> sp.(Guh huh) Fabaceae	Tree	Leaves, bark	0.30%
<i>Buchanania lanzan</i> sp. (Sah coo rae) Anacardiaceae	Tree	Leaves, bark	1.36%
<i>Dalbergia</i> sp (Sahree) Fabaceae	Tree	Twigs, leaves	0.30%
<i>Dioscorea</i> sp. (New-ay me amoo) Dioscoreaceae	Climber	Vine, leaves, twig	3.48%
<i>Embelia</i> sp. (Ta bla Chee) Primulaceae	Tree	Leaves	1.82%
<i>Embelia</i> sp (Ta blah chew) Primulaceae	Climber	Leaves	1.36%
<i>Entada rheedii</i> Spreng.(Rey match uh) Fabaceae	Climber	Whole plant, bark	5.83%
<i>Grewia eriocarpa</i> Juss. (Sah bloh bley) Tiliaceae	Tree	Bark	0.45%
<i>Grewia</i> sp.(Sah gwee soh) Malvaceae	Tree	Leaves, Bark	0.45%
<i>Lagerstroemia</i> sp. (Duh koh ha) Lythraceae	Tree	Leaves	1.06%
<i>Phoenix loureiroi kunth</i> (Lee kaw doo) Arecaea	Tree	Leaves	1.06%
<i>Radermachera</i> (La bodeh) Araliaceae	Tree	Leaves, bark	20.80%
<i>Spondias pinnata</i> (L.f.) Kurz (Makoo) Anacardiaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.45%
Unidentified (Hche)	Tree	Leaves	1.51%
<i>Shorea obtusa</i> (La boh) Dipterocarpaceae	Tree	Bark	0.61%
Unidentified (Noh) Poaceae	Grass	Whole plant	0.76%
<i>Spahtolobus</i> sp. (Qui Bah Moo) Fabaceae	Climber	Leaves	0.76%
Unidentified (Soh saw doe)	Unidentified	Undeterminable	3.18%
<i>Solanum torvum</i> Sw. (Suh go caw) Solanaceae	Shrub	Leaves	0.15%
<i>Cissus hastata</i> Miq. (Tah Pah Gwah) Vitaceae	Climber	Vines	0.61%

The elephants consumed 96.06% browse species (bamboo, climbers, trees, shrubs, and herbs) and only 0.76% grasses; 3.18% were unidentified species. The most consumed plant was two species of bamboo (50%), followed by thirteen species of trees (34%) (Table 2.2a). There was one new plant species (Tah Pah Gwah) added during the expedition, which was consumed at 0.61%. The remaining five unidentified species were found prior to the expedition, but were not identified by a botanist at the time. New samples of all six unidentified species were re-collected and identified by a botanist, with the exception of two species, which remain under review for ID. There was no significant difference between plants consumed by each elephant ($F=0.898$, $p=0.598$).

Elephant association

All six elephants showed varied social preferences. The male bulls were commonly observed on their own, or forming bachelor groups, while the other five elephants did not consistently segregate into distinctive groups.

Gen Thong is related to three other elephants. He is Dodo's brother, Mae Doom's nephew and Too Meh's grandson. For the young male, Gen Thong, 32 data points were collected where association to at least one other individual could not be determined. Gen Thong was touching another elephant for 25% of recorded observations, within reach of another elephant for 41% of recorded observations, and at a distance of 6 metres or greater for 34% of recorded observations (Figure 2.2b). When comparing Gen Thong's association to each elephant, he was observed touching Sri Prai (19%) and Mae Doom (6%) the most. He was within a trunk's reach of Sri Prai (16%) followed by Mae Doom (9%). The majority of his time was spent greater than 6 meters to Mae Doom (13%) and Too Meh (9%), followed by Sri Prai (6%) and Dodo (3%). The only interaction with Boon Rott was seen at the trunk's reach only at (6%).

The adult female, Mae Doom, had 111 data points collected where association to at least one other individual could be determined. Mae Doom was touching another elephant for 15% of observations, within reach of another elephant for 38% of recorded observations, and a distance of 6 meters or greater 47% of the time (Figure 2.2b). When touching another elephant, it was most commonly Too Meh (10%), followed by Dodo (3%), Sri Prai (3%) and Gen Thong (2%). Mae Doom was observed within a trunk's reach of Too Meh (17%) and Sri Prai (15%). Mae Doom was observed with Too Meh at a distance greater than 6 meters (19%), followed by Sri Prai (13%). No observations were collected between Mae Doom and Boon Rott.

For the oldest female, Too Meh, 90 data points were collected where association to at least one other individual could be determined. Too Meh was recorded touching another elephant 19% of the time, within reach of another elephant 34% of the time, and at a distance of 6 meters or greater for 47% of observation time (Figure 2.2b). No association was observed between male bull Boon Rott and Too Meh. The majority of time was spent between Mae Doom (38%) and Sri Prai (27%). Too Meh was only observed touching two other elephants (Mae Doom 13% and Sri Prai 6%), but was observed within trunk's reach of every elephant except Boon Rott. Dodo and Gen Thong remained in trunk reach at 4% and 2%, and were also observed for >6 meters or more at 2% and 6%.

Looking at Boon Rott, the male unrelated to the rest of the elephant herd, 5 data points were collected to at least one other individual. Boon Rott was recorded touching another elephant 20% of the time, within reach of another elephant 40% of observation time, and at a distance of 6 metres or greater 40% of the time (Figure 2.2b). The only interactions observed were those of Gen Thong (40%) and Sri Prai (60%). Boon Rott had varied interactions with Sri Prai, only one touching data point was observed (20%), and 6 meters or greater (40%). Boon Rott was at a trunk's reach with other male bull Gen Thong at 40%.

For Dodo, 58 data points were collected where association to at least one other individual could be determined. Dodo was recorded touching another elephant for 9% of observations, within reach of another elephant for 28% of observations, and a distance of 6 metres or greater 64% of the time (Figure 2.2b). No association was observed between Dodo and Boon Rott. Dodo was rarely observed touching an elephant (Sri Prai 3%, Mae Doom 5%). When observed, Dodo would be at trunk's reach from Mae Doom (10%) followed by Sri Prai (9%). However, Dodo spent more time at 6 metres or greater with Sri Prai at 40%. Dodo spent the majority of the data points with Sri Prai (52%), followed by Mae Doom (24%), and Too Meh (7%).

Finally, Sri Prai, a young female that is unrelated to the rest of the elephant herd, was observed for a total of 109 points. Sri Prai was recorded touching another elephant 14%, within trunk's reach of another elephant at 35%, and at a distance of 6 metres or greater at 51% the remainder of the time (Figure 2.2b). Sri Prai spent the majority of her time with Mae Doom (31%), followed by Too Meh (28%) and Dodo (27%). Sri Prai is the only elephant that was observed touching each elephant, Too Meh (6%), Gen Thong (5%), both Dodo and Mae Doom (3%) and lastly Boon Rott (1%). For the majority of the data observed, she remained within a trunk's reach, Sri Prai spent 13% with Too and Mae Doom and 6% with Gen Thong and Dodo.

Figure 2.2b. Percentage of observed time each elephant spent within a certain distance of the other elephants.

2.3. Discussion and conclusions

Activity budgets

Foraging was the dominant behaviour of all seven elephants. Foraging percentages were roughly similar (47% in 2022, 52% in 2019, 63% in 2018 and 59% in 2017) (Gale and Hammer 2018, Johncola et al. 2019), corroborating findings by Ahamed (2015) and Sukumar (2003) with values between 45% to 75%.

The elephants spent also 16% of their time walking, 8% exploring and 7% socialising.

These percentages clearly differ from those of captive elephants. Rees (2009) found that captive elephants spend less time foraging (ranging from 25 to 42%) and more time performing stereotypic behaviours commonly referred to as post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) – repeated movement patterns with no apparent function, such as swaying, pacing or standing motionless, a behaviour that is almost entirely absent in our study. Two studies conducted on captive elephants in India (29%) and Tampa Florida, USA (19-44%) also found that captive elephants only spent a small portion of activity budgets foraging (Varma et al. 2008, Lukacs et al. 2016).

All this corroborates our hypothesis that the behaviours observed by the semi-wild KSES elephants closely mimic those of wild elephant populations and that the distinctive behavioural variation between captive populations and wild populations is indicative of the lack of opportunity for captive animals to exhibit natural behaviours. We therefore posit that welfare conditions for captive elephants would be improved significantly if more time was allocated for them to express natural behaviours such as foraging, socialising and walking.

Foraging

This expedition recorded 23 species eaten by the elephants in 661 minutes of foraging time. This is more than double the amount of plant species of the 2018 expedition and six further new plants species since the 2019 expedition. The large increase in browse species diversity may be due to wetter and more humid conditions, which favour plant growth and diversification. The elephants are also curious, constantly foraging on new and diverse plant species. The unidentified plant species were consumed at a rate of 3%.

In 2022 the elephants displayed a strong preference towards bamboo at 50%, much more than the 15% of 2019. The preference for bamboo may be connected to increased bamboo availability due to higher humidity, which bamboo does well in.

All expeditions recorded a preference for browsing species (96% in 2022, 85% in 2019, 91% in 2018 and 85% in 2017). The 2022 peak may also be connected to the higher humidity.

In general, food preferences vary significantly with seasonal changes and availability. Browsing species are preferred during the wet season while during the dry season, there is an increase in grasses or graze species. For example, Roy and Chowdhury (2014) have shown a shift from 89% browsing species in the wet season to 76% graze species in the dry season in Bengal, whereas Sukumar (1989) reports a shift to grasses in tropical dry forest.

There are currently no guidelines for the adequate nutrition for elephants in captivity in Thailand. The KSES paper (Schwarz et al. 2020) on browse species is the first of its kind and aims to establish feeding guidelines for elephants in captivity that are closer to their natural diet.

Association

Unlike our 2019 expedition, we did see an increase of segregation into distinctive groups, among our six elephants. While our 2019 expedition indicated a close association (touching distance) observed for the young male Gen Thong with the two adult females Mae Doom and Too Meh, the 2022 expedition indicated a significant decline in association, specifically regarding touching distance with mature female elephants. However, it is noteworthy to mention that Sri Prai, our youngest female, had the most touching distance interaction with Gen Thong (19%). Our two youngest elephants were in close proximity and had the opportunity to touch, which is an important aspect of Asian elephant social structure (Makecha et al. 2012).

Boon Rott was observed associating with Sri Prai and Gen Thong, which differs from the 2019 expedition. In the 2019 expedition, 147 associations were collected, however, in the 2022 expedition only 5 associations were observed. Boon Rott was observed on his own during the majority of observations. Males often separate from family units once they reach adulthood (de Silva and Wittemyer 2012). This is not surprising, since elephants are usually segregated into distinctive groups: the old females, adult females, young males and solitary male bachelors (Johncola et al. 2019). This change in behaviour may be attributed to Boon Rott maturing as a bull elephant. Since the 2018 expedition, Boon Rott has experienced his first period of musth, meaning he is now a sexually mature elephant.

Dodo was a new addition to KSES in 2019, and while the expedition of 2019 concluded that Dodo spent a majority of observations solitary, the 2022 expedition indicated a significant increase in association patterns. Out of the three male bulls in KSES, Dodo seems to adapt to associate with the female and male groups respectively. However, Dodo is still relatively new to KSES, and more research is required to examine his social patterns.

Additionally, Sri Prai is our youngest female elephant, and also the newest addition to our herd. Sri Prai was the only elephant to be observed associating with all of the elephants. Sri Prai spent a majority of time associating with Too Meh, followed by Mae Doom, which is not surprising, since females tend to form a herd, as seen in previous studies (de Silva and Wittemyer 2012). While spending a collective time with the female herd, Sri Prai also spent a significant amount of time with Dodo, which may indicate a potential mating match, since Sri Prai has reached maturity.

Natural behaviours and the implication for captive elephants

Citizen science research work with Biosphere Expeditions has allowed KSES to compare the natural behaviours and foraging habits displayed by semi-wild Asian elephants to those of wild Asian elephants, showing that the KSES semi-wild herd has more in common with wild Asian elephants. Our argument is therefore that the ethical route for captive animals should be reintroduction into semi-wild conditions similar to the KSES situation, rather than being completely “re-wilded” when there is no space anyhow and significant potential for conflict with humans. KSES can act as a showcase for others in this regard.

The expedition work has also allowed us to highlight areas for improvement in regard to the management of captive Asian elephant populations. For example, discrepancies exist in the amount of time elephants dedicate to foraging in captivity when compared to wild elephants. In addition, the lack of a diverse diet in captive elephant samples in comparison to wild elephants’ diet needs to be addressed. Based on the data collected by the expeditions, we argue that the amount and diversity of foliage, including more browse species, that captive elephant populations have access to, should be improved. In addition, adequate space management to allow roaming and social structure expression, can help minimise stress in both captive and wild populations.

This study’s contribution to elephant welfare and conservation

Knowledge gleaned through the expeditions on the diverse diet, foraging ecology and the behaviours of semi-wild Asian elephants allows KSES to make welfare standard and management recommendations for captive elephants and contribute to wild elephant conservation. This study also highlights the need for long term, repetitive studies on natural Asian elephant behaviour, social preferences and foraging ecology.

Outlook

More research is needed to improve data accuracy and to enable further publications. This was also only the third expedition including Dodo and the first expedition including Sri Prai as members of the study group. As such, expeditions should be repeated and continue to collect data.

As the elephants move to different areas of the forest throughout the study site, the forest composition differs, opening up new foraging opportunities, potentially adding species to the list of foraged plants. In this expedition alone, two new plant samples were added to the species list of plants consumed by the elephants. Furthermore, in years to come, as the number of elephants under KSES’s care increases, the data sets can be expanded to incorporate more individual elephants in different age/sex classes. As the data set grows, articles can be published in scientific journals to aid in conservation efforts of Asian elephants. Standards for captive elephant management can be proposed from the information obtained in this expedition.

Summary and action points for the next expedition

Key findings of this expedition:

- A continuing detailed description of the diets of elephants free-roaming in the forests of Northern Thailand; one new plant sample not previously recorded with two samples waiting on review by botanist.
- A description of the behavioural patterns of six semi-wild, free-roaming elephants to show the natural behaviours of elephants displayed at KSES compared to those in captivity.
- A description of the social patterns of six semi-wild, free-roaming elephants and how these patterns change over time.

Actions for the next expedition and future research:

- Continue to record observations for the elephant association and elephant activity data sets to ensure quantity and quality of data in order to elucidate with confidence patterns in behaviours.
- Following the KSES paper of Schwarz et al. (2020) on elephant diet, publish activity budget and association data in a peer-reviewed journal by 2025, in order to create an elephant management guide to be distributed to elephant venues in Thailand and around the world by 2026

2.4. Literature cited

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